

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

A Versatile Colorimetric Probe based on Thiosemicarbazide-Amine Proton Transfer

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1. Supporting Data

Figure S1. The synthesis of the naphthalimide-based chromophore with a thiosemicarbazide binding motif **1** was carried out following a modified literature procedure.^[1] *Reagents and conditions:* (a) Ethylamine, 1,4-dioxane, 8 h, 91%; (b) hydrazine monohydrate, 1,4-dioxane, 60 °C, 12 h, 81%; (c) phenyl isothiocyanate, acetonitrile, 82 °C, 3d, 49%.

Figure S2. Crystal structure of the naphthalimide-based chromophore **1** with a disordered chloroform solvate molecule ($1 \cdot \text{CHCl}_3$) with thermal ellipsoids shown at a 50% probability level. Grey, blue, red, green, and yellow ellipsoids correspond to carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, chlorine and sulfur, respectively. Single crystals of the chromophore suitable for X-ray were grown from an acetone-chloroform vapor diffusion process. Systematic absences were consistent with the orthorhombic space group $Fddd$, as determined via XPREP. Symmetry equivalent reflections were averaged to yield the set of unique data after removal of systematically absent reflections. The resulting 3418 reflections were used in the least squares refinement. The SHELXTL software package was used to solve the structure via direct methods. Subsequent least-squares refinement cycles (SHELXL) revealed the positions of the remaining non-hydrogen atoms of the ethyl group on the naphthalimide. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with independent anisotropic displacement parameters. Hydrogen atoms were placed in geometrically ideal positions and refined independently. An isotropic extinction parameter was not necessary. The weighting parameter was 0.053. Successful convergence was indicated by the maximum shift/error of 0.001 for the last cycle of least squares refinement. The largest peak in the

residual electron density map ($0.67 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$) was located 1.7 \AA away from the center of the disordered solvent molecule. The asymmetric unit is comprised of the chromophore with a dihedral angle between the phenyl and naphthalimide groups $>90^\circ$. Owing to this arrangement of aromatic substituents, the unit cell shows stacking of the naphthalimides along the a axis and stacking of the phenyl groups along the b axis in agreement with related structures reported in the literature.^[1] Inter-molecular hydrogen bonding between the C=O and all three N–H in the chromophore is clearly evident.

Figure S3. **A)** UV-Vis absorption spectra of chromophore **1** (orange line; in DMSO; $c = 0.076 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$) and upon titration with aliquots of diethylamine (purple lines), subsequently referred as complex **6**. **B)** Changes of the absorption maximum at $\lambda = 574 \text{ nm}$ of the spectra shown in (A) as a function of the molar equivalents of added diethylamine. **C)** UV-Vis absorption spectra of chromophore **1** (orange line; in DMSO; $c = 0.076 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$) and upon titration with aliquots of triethylamine (purple lines), subsequently referred as complex **7**. **D)** Changes of the absorption maximum at $\lambda = 574 \text{ nm}$ of the spectra shown in (C) as a function of the molar equivalents of added triethylamine.

Figure S4. **A)** Pictures documenting the reversible color change observed upon deprotonation and reprotonation of the chromophore. **B)** UV-Vis absorption spectra of chromophore **1**, the deprotonated chromophore formed upon addition of one equivalent of *n*-butylamine, and after addition of an equimolar quantity of tetrafluoroacetic acid (in DMSO; $c = 0.076 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$).

Figure S5. Comparison of the ^1H NMR spectra (400 MHz, 297.2 K, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) of chromophore **1** ($c = 0.017 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and an equimolar complex with *n*-butylamine (**2**) ($c = 0.014 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and **3** obtained by deprotonation of the chromophore **1** with potassium *tert*-butoxide ($c = 0.0106 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Figure S6. ^1H , ^{13}C HMBC spectrum of the chromophore **1** (400 MHz; 297.2 K; $\text{DMSO-}d_6$; $c = 0.017 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Figure S7. ^1H , ^{13}C HMBC spectrum of **2** obtained by addition of equimolar amounts of *n*-butylamine to chromophore **1** (400 MHz; 297.2 K; $\text{DMSO-}d_6$; $c = 0.014 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Figure S8. ^1H , ^{13}C HMBC spectrum of **3** obtained by deprotonation of the chromophore **1** with potassium *tert*-butoxide (400 MHz; 297.2 K; DMSO- d_6 ; $c = 0.0106 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Figure S9. Comparison of the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectra (400 MHz, 297.2 K, DMSO- d_6) of chromophore **1** ($c = 0.017 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and an equimolar complex with *n*-butylamine (**2**) ($c = 0.014 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and **3** obtained by deprotonation of the chromophore **1** with potassium *tert*-butoxide ($c = 0.0106 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Figure S10. Comparison of the ^1H NMR spectra (400 MHz, 297.2 K, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) of chromophore **1** ($c = 0.015 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) the complex after the addition of *n*-butylamine and after addition of TFA.

Figure S11. **A**) Ratio of the absorbance intensities (A_{550}/A_{413}) recorded at 550 and 413 nm after exposure of a cellulose paper imbibed with chromophore **1** for 10 min to the vapor phase of different aqueous amine solutions (80 mM). Amines are ordered according to decreasing volatility from left to right. **B**) Overview of the vapor pressure at 20 °C of the different amines employed in **(A)** (values for aniline and putrescine reported for 25 °C).^[2] **C**) Ratio of the absorbance intensities (A_{550}/A_{413}) recorded at 550 and 413 nm after exposure of a cellulose paper imbibed with chromophore **1** for 10 min to the vapor phase different solvents containing *n*-butylamine (80 mM). **D**) Overview of the vapor pressure at 20 °C for the solvents employed in **(C)**.

Figure S12. Plot of the ratio of the absorbance intensities (A_{550}/A_{413}) recorded at 550 and 413 nm after exposure of a cellulose paper imbibed with chromophore **1** to the vapor phase of an aqueous *n*-butylamine solutions (80 mM) for different times between 1 and 15 min.

Figure S13. A) Absorbance of the chromophore-loaded paper (measured in reflectance mode) before and after consecutive exposure to the vapors of an aqueous *n*-butylamine solution (80 mM; 10 min), aqueous trifluoroacetic acid (80 mM; 1 h), and again an aqueous *n*-butylamine solution (80 mM; 10 min). **B)** Photographs showing the visual color change of the corresponding chromophore-loaded filter paper after each exposure described in (A).

Figure S14. **A)** Absorbance of the chromophore-loaded paper (measured in reflectance mode) before and after the gas phase of an aqueous *n*-butylamine solution (80 mM) of the same concentration was collected with a syringe and pumped through the sensor. **B)** Photographs showing the visual color change of the corresponding chromophore-loaded filter paper before and after the exposure described in (A).

Figure S15. **A)** Absorbance of the chromophore-loaded paper (measured in reflectance mode) before and after 10 min of exposure to the atmosphere of a piece of salmon that had been stored for 1 week under ambient conditions.

2. Supporting Experimental Section

2.1. Materials and Instrumentation

All reagents and solvents were purchased as analytical grade from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification. 1, 4-Dioxane and acetonitrile were purchased dry over molecular sieves from Sigma-Aldrich. All spectroscopic investigations were carried out with spectroscopy grade solvents. Deuterated solvents were purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc. Cellulose quantitative filter paper (424) was purchased from VWR. Salmon was purchased in a local grocery store.

NMR Spectroscopy was carried out at 297.2 K on a Bruker Avance DPX 400 spectrometer at frequencies of 400.19 MHz for ^1H nuclei and 100.63 MHz for ^{13}C nuclei. Spectra were calibrated to the residual solvent peak of DMSO- d_6 (2.50 ppm ^1H NMR; 39.52 ppm ^{13}C NMR). Data were evaluated with the MestReNova software suite (v 12.0) and all chemical shifts δ are reported in parts per million (ppm) with coupling constant in Hz (multiplicity: s = singlet, d = doublet, dd = double doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, br = broad signal).

High resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were recorded as service measurements at the mass spectrometry service of the Institute of Chemistry of the University of Fribourg. Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) data were acquired on a Bruker FTMS 4.7T BioAPEX II equipped with a ComiSource 1.0 and operated in the positive ionization mode.

Melting points were measured on a BÜCHI Melting Point B-540 device.

Solution phase UV-Vis spectra in the wavelength range of 350–800 nm were recorded on a JASCO V670 using quartz cuvettes with a path length of 1 cm. Reflectance spectra in the wavelength range of 100–1100 nm were recorded with an Ocean Optics QEPro high performance spectrometer fixed in an Axio Scope A.1 microscope. An objective lens with a 5-fold magnification was used and the focus was adjusted on the sample surface resulting in a spot size of approximately 0.3 cm from which the diffuse reflectance was recorded. The corresponding Spectra were recorded before and after any type of vapor exposure and the data were acquired with Oceanview software and absorbance spectra were obtained by applying the reflectance/absorbance conversion ($A = \log(1/R)$).

Photographs were taken with a Nikon D7100 digital camera equipped with a AF-S DX Zoom-NIKKOR 18-135mm lens (f/3.5-5.6G IF-ED).

Airborne amine gases/vapours in the gas volume of closed containers were measured with GASTEC amine detector tubes (#180; amines; range 5-100 ppm) and a GASTEC sampling pump model GV-110S.

X-ray crystallography was conducted at the small-molecule crystallography core user facility at the University of Chicago using a Bruker D8 Venture dual Cu/Mo source instrument equipped with a PHOTON 100 CMOS detector.

2.2. Methods and Procedures

UV-Vis spectroscopy. DMSO stock solutions were prepared with defined concentrations of chromophore **1** ($c = 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), *n*-butylamine ($c = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), diethylamine ($c = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), triethylamine ($c = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), as well as trifluoroacetic acid ($c = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$). For titrations of the chromophore with different amines, the spectrum of 0.6 mL of the chromophore solution diluted in 1 mL of DMSO was measured, 10 μL aliquots of the amine solution were consecutively added, the solution was stirred and allowed to equilibrate for 1 min, before the measurement of each additional spectrum. The investigation of the reversibility of the process was carried out following the same procedure to prepare a solution with equimolar amounts of chromophore **1** and *n*-butylamine ($c = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), before an equimolar amount of the TFA solution ($c = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) was added and measurement of the corresponding absorption spectrum.

NMR spectroscopy. In an NMR tube, 15 mg of the chromophore were dissolved in 2 mL of DMSO- d_6 ($c = 1.92 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and followed by the addition of one equivalent of butylamine (3.8 μL). The chromophore and the complex were characterized by NMR measurements including ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, $^1\text{H},^{13}\text{C}$ HMBC, as well as $^1\text{H},^{13}\text{C}$ and $^1\text{H},^{15}\text{N}$ HSQC spectroscopy. The same procedure was used for the preparation of the corresponding complexes with 1 equivalent of diethylamine, 3 equivalents of trimethylamine, as well as 1 equivalent of potassium *tert*-butoxide. The reversible proton transfer was demonstrated by addition of TFA (2.9 μL) to the corresponding solution of the complex in DMSO- d_6 and subsequent characterization by NMR spectroscopy.

Chromophore immobilization on cellulose paper. Solutions of chromophore **1** in acetone were prepared ($c = 10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$). Circularly-shaped cellulose paper with a diameter of 0.5 cm was completely immersed in the chromophore solution for 10 s, the paper was removed from the solution, left to dry under ambient conditions for 30 min in a ventilated fume hood, and

the residual solvent was removed by placing the paper in a 50 mL round-bottom flask and applying vacuum ($5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar) for 30 min.

Exposure to amine vapors. Aqueous *n*-butylamine solutions of defined concentration ($c = 1, 1.5, 2, 10, 20, 40$ and 100 mmol L^{-1}) were prepared and 5 mL of these solutions were each placed in cylindrical screw-cap glass vials (20 mL). The vials were closed and the solutions were left standing under ambient conditions for 4 h to permit for a liquid-gas phase equilibration. The relative amine vapor concentrations in the gas phase of these vials were determined with the GASTEC amine detector tubes and sampling pump. A single pump stroke was applied per sample and the read-out was done after stabilization (30 s). For measurements of *n*-butylamine vapor concentrations, the correction factor of 1.6 was applied as provided by the supplier of the detector tubes. The vapor concentrations of *n*-butylamine were determined to 3, 6, 8, 29, 64, 128, 224 ppm for aqueous solutions with concentrations of $c = 1, 1.5, 2, 10, 20, 40$ and 100 mmol L^{-1} , respectively. To expose samples of the chromophore-loaded cellulose paper, the screw cap of the glass vial was exchanged against a cap to which the chromophore loaded paper was attached for a defined exposure time (10 min). The exposure was carried out with three distinct samples and reflectance spectra for all samples were recorded before and immediately after exposure. Following the same procedure, solutions of $c = 80 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$ of *n*-butylamine in water were prepared corresponding to a vapor concentration of ~ 200 ppm. Then, loaded chromophore cellulose papers were exposed for 30 seconds, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 15 minutes, respectively. The color change was monitored by absorbance measurements directly after the exposure.

In the same way, hexane, tetrahydrofuran, ethyl acetate, acetonitrile, ethanol, and methanol solutions of *n*-butylamine ($c = 80 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$) as well as aqueous solutions with a concentration of $c = 80 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$ of diethylamine, triethylamine, piperidine, tributylamine, pyridine, aniline, putrescine, and ammonia were prepared and 5 mL of each were filled in cylindrical screw-cap glass vials (20 mL). The loaded chromophore cellulose papers were exposed for 10 minutes and the color change monitored by absorbance measurements directly after the exposure time.

10 mL of neat trifluoroacetic acid was filled in a cylindrical screw-cap glass vial (20 mL). Samples of the chromophore-loaded cellulose paper were exposed for a defined time (30 sec) to the respective vapor phases after liquid-gas phase equilibration for 4 h. Collection of the gas phase of an *n*-butylamine solution was carried out with a syringe (10 mL) from B Braun and the amine vapor was pumped through cellulose paper immediately after collection.

2.3. Synthetic Procedures and Analytical Data

Unless otherwise noted, all reactions were carried out in dried Schlenk glassware in an inert nitrogen atmosphere.

6-Bromo-2-ethyl-benzo[de]isoquinoline-1,3-dione (4). 4-Bromo-1,8-naphthalic anhydride (4.0 g, 14 mmol) and ethylamine (1.36 mL, 70% in H₂O, 16 mmol) were dispersed in 1,4-dioxane (170 mL) and heated to reflux for 9 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and precipitated into deionized water (700 mL). The precipitate was collected by filtration, thoroughly washed with deionized water, and dried *in vacuo* to yield **4** (4.0 g, 13.2 mmol, 94%) as an off-white solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 8.59 (dd, 1H, *ArH*), 8.56 (dd, 1H, *ArH*), 8.35 (d, 1H, *ArH*), 8.23 (d, 1H, *ArH*), 8.01 (dd, 1H, *ArH*), 4.08 (q, 2H, *CH*₂), 1.22 (t, 3H, *CH*₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 163.1, 163.0 (2C, C=O), 133.0, 131.9, 131.3, 130.2, 129.5, 129.2, 128.7, 123.2, 122.5 (10C, *C-Ar*), 35.3 (*CH*₂), 13.4 (*CH*₃). HRMS (ESI): calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀NO₂Br: 303.9973 ([M+H]⁺); found: 303.9973. m.p.: 158.1–161.2 °C.

2-Ethyl-6-hydrazino-benzo[de]isoquinoline-1,3-dione (5). 6-Bromo-2-ethyl-benzo[de]isoquinoline-1,3-dione **4** (1.00 g, 3.3 mmol) was dispersed in 1,4-dioxane (100 mL) and the solution was heated to 60 °C. Hydrazine monohydrate (20 mL, 0.36 mol) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 18 h. The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and precipitated into deionized water (1 L). The precipitate was collected by filtration, thoroughly washed with deionized water, and dried *in vacuo* to yield **5** (0.69 g, 2.6 mmol, 81%) as a yellow solid, which was used without further purification for subsequent reactions. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 9.09 (s, 1H, *NH*), 8.60 (dd, 1.01 Hz, 1H, *ArH*), 8.42 (dd, 1H, *ArH*), 8.29 (d, 1H, *ArH*), 7.63 (dd, 7.43 Hz, 1H, *ArH*), 7.24 (d, 1H, *ArH*), 4.65 (s, 2H, *NH*₂), 4.05 (q, 2H, *CH*₂), 1.18 (t, 3H, *CH*₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ = 163.5, 162.7 (2C, C=O), 153.2, 134.1, 130.5, 129.3, 128.2, 124.1, 121.8, 118.4, 107.4, 104.0 (10C, *ArC*), 34.2 (*CH*₂), 13.3 (*CH*₃). HRMS (ESI): calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃N₃O₂: 256.1086 ([M+H]⁺); found: 256.1087.

2-(2-Ethyl-1,3-dioxo-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-benzo[de]isoquinolin-6-yl)-*N*-phenyl hydrazine-1-carbothioamide (1). 2-Ethyl-6-hydrazino-benzo[de]isoquinoline-1,3-dione **5** (0.4 g, 1.56 mmol) was dissolved in MeCN (80 mL) and the solution was heated to reflux (82 °C). Phenyl isothiocyanate (0.2 mL, 1.72 mmol) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 72h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and the formed precipitate was collected by filtration, thoroughly washed with MeCN, and dried *in vacuo* to

yield **1** (0.3 g, 0.76 mmol, 49%) as a green solid. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ = 10.09 (br. s, 2H, NH), 9.86 (br. s, 1H, NH), 8.70 (d, J = 8.44 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.46–8.56 (m, 1H, ArH), 8.42 (d, J = 8.31 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.78 (dd, J = 8.31, 7.46 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.43 (d, J = 6.97 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.31 (t, J = 7.76 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.12–7.19 (m, 1H, ArH), 6.99 (d, J = 8.31 Hz, 1H, ArH), 4.07 (q, J = 6.93 Hz, 2H, CH_2), 1.20 (t, J = 7.03 Hz, 3H, CH_3). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ = 181.30 (1C, C=S), 163.4, 162.8 (2C, C=O), 149.9, 139.0 (2C, ArC-NH), 133.6, 130.8, 129.4, 128.9, 127.9, 126.0, 125.2, 124.8, 121.8, 119.4, 111.5, 105.4 (12C, ArC), 29.6 (1C, CH_2), 13.2 (1C, CH_3). HRMS (ESI): calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: 413.1043 ($[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$) found: 413.1044. m.p.: 221.5–223.2 °C.

3. Supporting Molecular Characterization

^1H NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^1H , ^1H -COSY NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^1H , ^{13}C -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^1H , ^{13}C -HMBC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^1H , ^{15}N -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^1H NMR spectrum ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 400 MHz) of **2**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 101 MHz) of **2**.

$^1\text{H}, ^1\text{H}$ -COSY NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **2**.

$^1\text{H}, ^{13}\text{C}$ -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **2**.

^1H , ^{13}C -HMBC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **2**.

$^1\text{H}, ^{13}\text{N}$ -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **2**.

^1H NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **3**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 101 MHz) of **3**.

^1H , ^{13}C -HMBC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **3**.

^1H , ^{15}N -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **3**.

^1H NMR spectrum ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 400 MHz) of **4**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 101 MHz) of **4**.

^1H NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of **5**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 101 MHz) of **5**.

^1H NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of complex **6** formed by the deprotonation with diethylamine.

^{13}C NMR spectrum ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 101 MHz) of complex **6** formed by the deprotonation with diethylamine.

^1H , ^{13}C -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of complex **6** formed by the deprotonation with diethylamine.

^1H , ^{13}C -HMBC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of complex **6** formed by deprotonation with diethylamine.

^1H NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of complex **7** formed by the deprotonation with triethylamine.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 101 MHz) of complex **7** formed by the deprotonation with triethylamine.

^1H , ^{13}C -HSQC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of complex **7** formed by the deprotonation with triethylamine.

^1H , ^{13}C -HMBC NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) of complex 7 formed by deprotonation with triethylamine.

4. Supporting References

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